

THE USAGE OF STORYTELLING IN PRIMARY CLASSES TO IMPROVE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Annotation: This article deals with the usage of storytelling technique in young learners' learning languages to enhance their speaking and communicative abilities. The main aim of the issue is analyzing the advantages of stories in learning languages. Pointing their educational, cultural and upbringing effects on children.

Key words: Second language, acquisition, instruction, evidence, aspects, teaching process, primary, education.

Abstract: Communicative approach at language teaching has been widely recognized in the field of second language acquisition (SLA) over three decades. Currently, the various educational institutions' teachers try to teach speaking to their students in order to improve their communicative skills. As a result, tedious and ineffective methods as grammar-translation methods have been rejected. Consequently, storytelling method had been improved for supporting student's communicative skill. Storytelling is helpful in the language learning process, for it has the characteristic of being a motivating factor. The learner is completely absorbed into the story as it is a good way to combine instruction and entertainment.

Storytelling is the use of stories or narratives as a communication tool to value, share, and capitalize on the knowledge of individuals. Stories provide a powerful metaphor, framework, and set of practical processes for resolving issues, educating ourselves, and pursuing our goals. Storytelling can be a powerful element of communication process, being equally as textbooks and essays.

In the classroom, storytelling will help students remember things. When lecturers tell stories, students recall them. Only good stories, on the other hand, are lost forever. A good story is simple to recall. The majority of the stories that the student memorizes are both amusing and sad. It has everything to do with the relaxation of emotions at the moment. It will be remembered for the rest of their lives because it has an effect on their emotions. Furthermore, when the students hear the fascinating tales, their attention span will improve. It means that when they pay close attention to what the lecturers are saying, their memory will improve.

From an educational standpoint, as M. Brown (2009) points out, it is well known that students recall and learn well from stories. Furthermore, many cultures and

religions depend on the mode of instruction. For example, the Quran in Islam has been organized in narrative and stories so that Muslims can learn from the sentences and remember the rules that are embedded in it. It's also been shown that telling a story will help you remember things.

- Educational significance

According to research, storytelling has educational value. The importance of storytelling as an effective instructional tool for developing skills across the curriculum, as well as self-concept and self-esteem, has recently been recognized. Reading, writing, and math skills, as well as exposure to general principles in the sciences and social studies, have always been considered fundamental to education. Storytelling should be used to supplement training in all of these fundamentals, since storytelling is fundamental to humanity.

Listening to stories involves students in the storytelling process. Storytelling is a reemerging as an art that can bridge educational gap between the external world of 'doing' and the internal world of 'becoming' while C. Savvidou (2010), states that the educative function of stories is chiefly to equip students with knowledge that will later prove to be useful. Storytelling as a teaching tool will help make any content more engaging and meaningful.

According to Tobias (2008,), there is another important factor when selecting stories and it is related to storyteller himself: "Choose your stories wisely. If you don't like a story, don't tell it, because the child will perceive that you are not enjoying, and neither will (s)he. Choose stories that have some relevance in the life of the child and about something you can learn and enjoy together." On the other hand, Cameron (2001) also proposed several ideas that he considered to be taken into account when selecting stories. Here is a summary of them:

- The stories need to be motivating, fun and interesting for the children.
- Characters need to include fantastic beings and animals from wonderful worlds, who are able to gain their attention and empathy.
- Stories should provide positive feelings about their own culture.
- The argument must be clear and structured (formulation of a problem, different situations linked to each other and the resolution of the problem).
- There must be a balance between dialogue and narration, as well as repetition of grammar and vocabulary patterns, and include new vocabulary, but not in excess so that the story is understandable but does not discourage children.

In education, the once-forgotten, but well-proven method of "storytelling" is being actively introduced, which received the newfangled name "storytelling" - from the English storytelling: story-history and telling-representation, first used by the head of a US corporation, David Armstrong, to improve the company's performance

and quickly train newcomers, where “one of the principles is the connection between theory and practice”.

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Currently, this method has proven to be an effective means of building external and internal communications, communicating information to the audience by telling a touching, funny, sometimes instructive story with real or fictional characters. At the same time, the information is firmly assimilated, since it carries a semantic load.

Many authors consider Storytelling to be one of the most widely used and highly valued techniques in Early Childhood Education, especially in the second language learning. At this age, children are able to transform anything fantastic into a real thing through their imagination. Therefore, there must be books in the classroom so that children can touch them, observe them and experiment with them. Below it is mentioned some of the compelling reasons that different authors provide in order to focus the work.

In conclusion it is clear to say that communicative and speaking abilities play a vital role in studying a foreign language at school. Smooth speech helps students to retrieve specific information, and also allows them to learn other forms of speech activities, such as oral speech. Students develop their knowledge of a foreign language by using speaking skills to correct known information, assimilate commonly encountered syntactic constructs, language stamps and symbols involuntarily.

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